

A Case Report of Juvenile Myelomonocytic Leukemia in a Child: An Uncommon Presentation

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Abstract:

Background: This case report highlights an uncommon presentation of JMML in a male child, stressing the significance of early detection and coordinated management to improve patient outcomes.

Case Report: A 2-year-old boy exhibited symptoms of overall weakness, a progressively enlarging abdomen for 6-7 months, and occasional bouts of fever. Clinical examination revealed distinctive facial features, hepatosplenomegaly, and signs suggestive of Noonan syndrome. Laboratory investigations showed significant leukocytosis, monocytosis, anemia, and thrombocytopenia. Bone marrow examination and next-generation sequencing validated JMML's diagnosis with a germline NRAS mutation. Given the absence of a suitable sibling donor and financial limitations, the patient received azacitidine (AZA) chemotherapy as a preparatory step for hematopoietic stem cell transplantation (HSCT).

Discussion: This case underscores the complexity of diagnosing JMML, particularly in patients with overlapping congenital syndromes like Noonan syndrome. Molecular analysis played a crucial role in confirming the diagnosis. Despite the challenges, the patient responded well to AZA, highlighting its potential as a bridging therapy to HSCT. Early and accurate diagnosis and a multidisciplinary treatment approach are essential for improving outcomes in JMML patients.

Conclusion: This case implies the significance of promptly identifying and managing JMML, especially when it presents with syndromic features. Azacitidine demonstrates potential as a transitional treatment, while HSCT remains the definitive therapy.

Keywords: Juvenile myelomonocytic leukemia, NRAS gene mutation, azacitidine, hematopoietic stem cell transplantation (HSCT).

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Introduction

JMML (Juvenile myelomonocytic leukemia) is an uncommon and persistent clonal disorder of the hematopoietic system. It is marked by atypical cell proliferation from the granulocytic and monocytic lineages, making diagnosis difficult due to its wide range of clinical presentations.

JMML accounts for 2-3% of pediatric leukemias, with an annual incidence of 1-2 cases per million individuals. It predominantly affects infants and young children and is considerably rarer than acute myeloid leukemia (AML) [1].

This report details JMML case in a child, highlighting its atypical presentation and the associated diagnostic challenges. This case, reported within a tertiary care center in North-East India, highlights the importance of early recognition of such rare hematologic conditions. Through this report, we aim to add to the increasing body of research on JMML, emphasizing the importance of promptly identifying and managing the condition to improve patient outcomes.

Case report

A 2-year-old boy was initially presented to clinical hematology department of a tertiary care center with complaints of overall weakness and a gradually enlarging abdomen over 6-7 months. The mother also reported occasional episodes of fever over the past year. The patient weighed 9kg and was 75cm tall. During the general physical examination, notable facial characteristics were observed, including a prominent philtrum, widely low-set ears, spaced eyes, micrognathia, high-arched palate, short neck, and pectus carinatum. Additionally, bilateral pedal edema, anemia, and short stature were noted. Systemic examination revealed hepatosplenomegaly, with the liver measuring 12cm and the spleen measuring 15cm in length.

There was no history of any bleeding disorder. So based on clinical features an underlying congenital disorder (Noonan syndrome) was sought. However, Mantoux test and TORCH panel were negative.

The initial standard laboratory tests demonstrated hemoglobin (Hb) concentration of 6.3g/dL, white blood cell (WBC) count of 40,300/mm³ with 24 nucleated red blood cells per 100 WBCs. Additionally, an absolute neutrophil count of 11,628/mm³, an absolute lymphocyte count of 14,382/mm³, an absolute monocyte count of 4923/mm³, along with platelet count of 80,000/mm³ were observed. Blood smear revealed microcytic hypochromic anaemia and leucocytosis with shift to left with (4% myelocytes and 3% metamyelocytes) along with thrombocytopenia. Predominantly a leucoerythroblastic blood picture with absolute monocytosis was noted.

The HbF level estimated was 2%. HRCT thorax revealed mild cardiomegaly with mild ground glass opacities in bilateral lung field. 2-D ECHO was within normal limits. An abdominal ultrasound revealed hepatosplenomegaly. BMA revealed cellular marrow with trilineage haematopoiesis. Bone marrow biopsy revealed cellular marrow with prominence of lymphocytes/haematogones. Peripheral blood immunophenotyping revealed 0.87% of myeloblast with shift to left and 12.19% of monocytes. Next-generation sequencing revealed germline NRAS mutation with a variant coding DNA of c.35G>A, p.Gly12Asp with a VAF of 44%. Our patient was diagnosed with JMML considering above clinical features as well as laboratory investigations.

Due to absence of a suitable sibling donor and financial limitations, the patient received AZA chemotherapy as a preparatory treatment for HSCT. The patient was initially started on oral 6-MP@50mg/m²/day. In view of no response, it was finally changed to Inj Azacytidine as a bridging therapy to HSCT. Following 12 cycles of AZA, the

patient showed significant improvement with decreased WBC count and reduced spleen size. Repeat investigations indicated a decrease in the percentage of monocytes with reduction in VAF frequency of the NRAS mutation. The patient is now planning for haploidentical HSCT at a higher center.

Discussion

The case presented here emphasizes the difficulty in diagnosing JMML due to its diverse clinical manifestations, stressing significance of affirming a high suspicion level, especially in unusual presentation scenarios.

JMML comprises 2-3% of childhood leukemias, predominantly affecting infants as well as young children, with median onset age of 1.8yrs and a greater incidence in males.

[1]. This aligns with our case, where the patient was a male child who began exhibiting symptoms at 1.8 years of age.

In this case, child presented with nonspecific symptoms including generalized weakness, enlarging abdomen, and occasional fever over several months. The patient's presentation with nonspecific symptoms, coupled with distinctive facial features suggestive of Noonan syndrome, initially posed diagnostic ambiguity. However, meticulous clinical evaluation, laboratory investigations, and molecular analysis ultimately confirmed the diagnosis of JMML, highlighting the importance of a multidisciplinary approach in reaching an accurate diagnosis. Molecular analysis revealed a germline NRAS mutation, a common genetic alteration associated with JMML.

In our case, the diagnosis of JMML was confirmed according to the most recent diagnostic standards set forth by the WHO in 2022. These revised criteria eliminate the inclusion of Histone-lysine N-methyltransferase 2A (KMT2A) rearrangements and no longer regard monosomy 7 as a cytogenetic requirement.

The updated guidelines underscore the significance of molecular diagnostic studies, especially those indicating activation of the RAS pathway [2]. WHO highlights the importance of molecular biology research, placing greater emphasis on genetic examinations, and encourages healthcare institutions to integrate molecular biology techniques [2].

Patients with JMML frequently encounter abdominal discomfort and respiratory challenges attributed to the enlargement of the spleen and liver. Approximately half of the patients also present with swollen lymph nodes, and some may have enlarged tonsils resulting from leukemic infiltrates. Chest X-rays may uncover lung

infiltrates, leading to symptoms like coughing as well as respiratory distress. Although involvement of CNS is rare, cutaneous manifestations are persistent which was consistent with our case as the child developed eczematous eruptions during treatment. Allogeneic HSCT stands as unique curative method, presenting a notable survival benefit compared to alternative treatments. HSCT provides the possibility of long-term survival without treatment in around 50% of patients. Nonetheless, it is associated with a significant relapse rate of 30-40% [3]. Effective treatment in this case involved utilizing both chemotherapy with AZA as a transitional step towards HSCT. This was accomplished despite the limitations of not having a compatible sibling donor and facing financial constraints.

Because DNA hypermethylation of certain genes contributes to JMML's aggressive nature, AZA, DNA hypomethylating agent, investigated as potential therapeutic option for the condition. Although not curative, AZA aids in diminishing the disease load before HSCT as well as in instances of relapse or refractory disease by eliciting diverse hematological and molecular responses. This contributes to enhanced overall survival rates.

AZA received approval from FDA (Food and Drug Administration) for JMML's treatment in March 2022 [4]. AZA has demonstrated the capacity to provide complete clinical remission in certain patients with JMML. Research conducted by Niemeyer et al. suggested that AZA alone can be considered a feasible treatment approach for children solely diagnosed with JMML [4]. Fabri et al. in Slovakia investigated new strategy involving the administration of AZA at dose of 75mg/m² over 1-7 days of a 28-day cycle as a preparatory treatment preceding HSCT. They reported positive responses and minimal adverse effects [5]. Certain research studies have observed long-lasting remission after AZA treatment [6], as well as the eradication of monosomy 7 clones in JMML without necessitating HSCT [7]. The patient underwent chemotherapy with AZA as a transitional treatment preceding HSCT. AZA demonstrated efficacy in decreasing disease severity and enhancing clinical indicators, underscoring its utility as a potential therapeutic choice for JMML patients who are not immediately eligible for HSCT.

Following 12 cycles of AZA therapy, the patient exhibited significant clinical improvement, characterized by decreased WBC count and reduced spleen size. Importantly, repeat investigations demonstrated a decrease in the percentage of monocytes, indicating a favorable response to treatment. However, the persistence of the NRAS mutation highlights the need for vigilant monitoring for disease recurrence or progression

post-transplantation. Jin Kang et al. in Korea presented an innovative therapeutic strategy for newly diagnosed JMML patients ineligible for transplantation. A conventional treatment was developed, delivered every 3weeks, comprising a conjugation of chemotherapy (Ara-C, etoposide, and vincristine) as well as differentiation therapy (isotretinoin). In cases of disease relapse or progression, a salvage regimen comprising chemotherapy (Ara-C, etoposide) along with differentiation therapy (low-dose Ara-C) given every 3-4weeks. Although the study involved only 5 JMML patients, this regimen was considered safe as well as effective [8]. In China, Feng et al. assessed an alternative treatment regimen encompassing decitabine, fludarabine, as well as cytarabine. They determined that this regimen was safe, effective, as well as feasible, attaining a response rate of 97%. However, they observed that rate of complete remission had been relatively modest, with primarily partial remissions [9].

New medications aiming at crucial pathways implicated in JMML development, like RAF/MEK/ERK/PI3K/AKT/mTOR, Src family multikinases, and JAK-STAT pathway inhibitors, are being explored in preclinical phases, particularly concerning the period before HSCT or during relapse. Trametinib, a MEK inhibitor, is presently undergoing prospective assessment by COG (Children's Oncology Group) in pediatric individuals suffering from JMML who have relapsed or are refractory to treatment [10]. Negative prognostic factors consist of being diagnosed at an older age (>2 years), having a platelet count below $33 \times 10^9/L$, as well as elevated age-adjusted HbF levels. These factors are correlated with poorer outcomes, such as decreased event-free and overall survival, post-HSCT [11,12]

Individuals with JMML carrying NRAS mutations exhibit significant clinical variability compared to other subtypes of JMML. A notable proportion of these patients experience relapse following allogeneic HCT, often accompanied by SETBP1 mutations. However, some patients with NRAS-mutated JMML achieve disease regression without undergoing HCT [10].

The main reason for treatment failure in JMML is disease relapse, which commonly happens within 4-6months following HSCT, with rare occurrences beyond 1 year. In some cases, a second HSCT has been successful in 30-50% of cases. Currently, targeted therapies are being investigated more extensively to diminish pre-transplant tumor burden and prevent post-HSCT relapse [3]. Opting for haploidentical HSCT at a specialized center underscores the significance of interdisciplinary cooperation and access to expert care in addressing rare hematologic disorders such as JMML. HSCT stands as the sole curative treatment for JMML,

presenting the opportunity for prolonged disease-free survival in suitable candidates.

Conclusion

In summary, this case emphasizes the difficulties in diagnosing and treating JMML and underscores the significance of promptly diagnosing, and effectively managing the condition to improve patient outcomes.

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